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BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY OF NAGALAND BAMBOO DEVELOPMENT AGENCY: CHALLENGES AND ISSUES FACED (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DIMAPUR SADAR DISTRICT).

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ABSTRACT

Naga people are known for its Bamboo Handicrafts. In usual Naga house, we will always come across many bamboo decorative items. Not only the Naga's are fond of bamboo products but the non-locals are also very curious about these products. There are various products which are made of bamboo such as Musical instruments like flute, mouth organ, Fish trapping baskets, Combs , Naga Belt, Mugs, Ceremonial hat etc. As Dimapur is a commercial hub and has a great potential for marketing of bamboo products. Following study is conducted by the researcher to find out the behavior of the consumers towards bamboo products and what are the bottlenecks which act as a barrier for the sustainability of these products. Finally this article also tries to know the challenges faces by the entrepreneurs while marketing their products inside and outside Nagaland.

Descriptive research design was adopted and the data is collected through primary and secondary sources which include questionnaire, personal interview, observation and internet. The method adopted for conducting survey is questionnaire & personal interview; Non Probability sampling technique was adopted under which Quota sampling method is being used for selecting the consumers on the basis of quota which falls under the age group from 18-40 years. The sample size was 140 (133 consumer and 6 entrepreneurs & 1 distributors).

The study found that Bamboo business has its future in Nagaland and it has huge potential to grow in the near future. Some problems like high manufacturing cost, lack of scientific farming and innovative promotion tools cause hindrance in the flow of business. Entrepreneurs also stated that they will find the solution to their problems and market it globally all over the world.

Keywords: Bamboo Products, Nagaland Bamboo Development Agency, people response towards bamboo products, Marketing tactics, Challenges and issues.

INTRODUCTION

The Word "Bamboo" derived from Dutch or Portuguese language. Bamboo generally belong from a grass family namely *Poaceae*. Bamboo has one special characteristic of growing fast within a short duration and without much hitch. Scientifically it is proved that it can grow within 60 days and within 4 years it can become a full flagged Bamboo plant. One important thing to note that it can survive upto 120 years which is good for its business purpose as they have more life span. Besides this, plantation of Bamboo plants is very simple in nature as compared to other types of farming. All these features makes it Unique from other natural resources to use it for commercial activity. History of Bamboo culture lies with Asian countries. Japan is one such country where bamboos are used in large quantity from decorating the house to making chopsticks. In India, bamboos are naturally grown all over the region (apart from Kashmir). If we consider its density of growth, it is widely found in the North eastern region namely-Nagaland, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Tripura, Mizoram etc.

Nagaland is one such state in India, where the plantation of Bamboo plants are very vast. It is also because of the geographical advantage and topography of the state. Not only Bamboo plants, even other vegetation grows at ease due to its moderate climate. There are many varieties of bamboo species grown in this part. Some species are as small as thumb size whereas there are species which grows hundreds of feet. "D. Gigantium" is one such species which are so big and heavy that one or two peoples can't carry it. It is tougher, stronger and more elastic in nature. Due to its widely available characteristics, Naga bamboo works in one of the most popular all over the world. "Hornbill Fest" which is an international fest held every year in the month of December. In this Fest bamboos are very widely used to signify the Naga heritage and culture. Nagaland Bamboo Development Agency popularly known as Nagaland Bamboo Resource Centre is state enterprise to promote the bamboo products in Nagaland. This Agency is an autonomous body under the chairmanship of Honorable Chief Minister of Nagaland. It was established in 2005 with the objective to take up bamboo both as a resource and as an enterprise. Along with that, there are many small-small entrepreneurs who are doing business of Bamboo products. Nagaland have 16 tribes in total, all these tribe has some speciality and unique way of crafting the bamboo products which are different from one another.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study sustainability of the Bamboo Handicrafts business in Nagaland and its growth potentialities.
2. To study the Challenges & Issues faced by entrepreneur to market their products within as well as outside the local boundaries.

MATERIAL & METHODS

This section consist of mainly the procedure and the method by which the research is conducted and the technique that is used to collect and analyze the data for the study. The main objectives

of the study is to identify how the Bamboo handicraft business in Nagaland will sustain over a longer period of time and what are the problem and issues faced by the Indigenous entrepreneurs to market their products and what are the possible ways to overcome it so that it will sustain for a longer period of time. Therefore the data for this research is taken in both primary and secondary ways. Dimapur city, the major commercial hub in Nagaland, has a heterogeneous mix of people from all over India, and for which it is also known as "Mini India". Dimapur town is the commercial hub of the state and is the magnet around which the economic and development activities of the district are centered; it is one of the fastest developing township of the North East. Though population is unknown so the researcher chosen the Non Probability Sampling with quota sampling techniques to get the sample and the regarding with sampling size about to 140 in that 133 are consumers, 1 distributor and 6 entrepreneurs: target audience is the youth from age between 18 to 40.

SWOT ANALYSIS OF NAGALAND BAMBOO DEVELOPMENT AGENCY:

A Study undertaken to identify the internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as its external opportunities and threats of NBDA.

Particulars	Helpful To achieve the objectives	Harmful To achieve the objectives
Internal Origin (attributes of the organization)	Strengths: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Backed by State Government. • Specialized Labour • Geographical competitiveness • Modern Equipment's • Widely available Resources(raw-material) 	Weaknesses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial Resources in not upto the expectation. • Labour turnover • High Pricing of Products • Poor Marketing and Advertising strategy.
External Origin (attributes of the environment)	Opportunities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Globalization • Potential to grow in other parts of Nagaland. • Adoption of Online Marketing strategy • People Awareness towards Environment Friendly products 	Threats: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing Competition due to liberalization. • Low GDP growth rate of India. • Inflation • Scientific Farming.

Note: This SWOT analysis is proposed based on the Researcher Observation and interviewing the different personnel engaged in the Bamboo business as well as NBDA Personnel and not through any secondary information.

Nagaland Bamboo Development Agency under the chairmanship of Honorable Chief Minister of the state was established with the main objective of promoting the bamboo products and growth

some cases price are very high as compared to other products which induces the customers to purchase a cheaper non environment friendly products due to price constraints.

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